

CULTURAL REALIAS AS TOOLS FOR INTEGRATION OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The integration of cultural realias into English language education has proven to enhance learners' proficiency by exposing them to authentic contexts. This study examines the role of cultural realias—such as visual aids, texts, artefacts, and multimedia—in promoting linguistic competence and cross-cultural understanding. Results indicate that using these materials improves vocabulary retention, cultural awareness, and engagement. The paper concludes that cultural realias are indispensable in English language teaching, fostering both linguistic and cultural integration.

Keywords: Cultural realias, cultural competence, visuals, texts, language, artefacts, cultural integration

Abstrakt: Madaniy realiyalarning ingliz tili ta'limiga integratsiyalashuvi o'quvchilarning haqiqiy kontekstlarga ochib berish orqali ularning malakasini oshirishi isbotlangan. Ushbu tadqiqot ko'rgazmali qo'llanmalar, matnlar, artefaktlar va multimedia kabi madaniy voqelikning lingvistik kompetentsiya va madaniyatlararo tushunishni rivojlantirishdagi rolini o'rganadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ushbu materiallardan foydalanish so'z boyligini saqlash, madaniy xabardorlik va faollikni yaxshilaydi. Maqolaning xulosasiga ko'ra, madaniy realiyalar ingliz tilini o'qitishda ajralmas bo'lib, til va madaniy integratsiyani rivojlantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Madaniy realiyalar, madaniy kompetentsiya, vizual tasvirlar, matnlar, til, artefaktlar, madaniy integratsiya

Introduction

In today's globalized world, mastering the English language extends beyond grammar and vocabulary. Cultural competence is a critical component of communication, as it shapes context, tone, and appropriateness. In translation, Realia (plural noun) are words and expressions for culture-specific material elements. The word realia comes from medieval Latin, in which it originally meant "the real things", i.e. material things, as opposed to abstract ones. The Bulgarian translators Vlahov and Florin, who were the first to carry out an in-

depth study of realia, coined the modern sense of the word. They indicate that since realia carry a very local overtone, they often pose a challenge for translation.[1] Realia must not be confused with terminology: the latter is primarily used in the scientific literature to designate things that pertain to the scientific sphere, and usually only appears in other kinds of texts to serve a very specific stylistic purpose. Realia, on the other hand, are born in popular culture, and are increasingly found in very diverse kinds of texts. Fiction, in particular, is fond of realia for the exotic touch they bring. Cultural realias, defined as authentic objects, materials, and media reflecting cultural practices, offer learners practical exposure to the nuances of English-speaking cultures. This paper investigates how cultural realias enhance the learning process, enabling learners to acquire both linguistic and cultural fluency. Culture is a "living" category, whose development is directly related to the development of society. In this regard, the content of the socio-cultural component will constantly change, enriched with new content. An integral part of the linguoculturological component is a specially selected homogeneous language material that reflects the culture of the country of the language being studied, as well as non-equivalent background vocabulary, non-verbal languages of gestures, facial expressions and everyday behavior. Nonequivalent vocabulary occupies a special place. It exists because it denotes national realias. Knowing realias is important when studying the culture and language of the country. The presence of a national-cultural component, which is absent in other languages, remains a constant sign of the belonging of words to linguistic and cultural material. Realia- realise; realia- "real", "real". "Realias are words and phrases that name objects that are characteristic of the life (everyday life, culture, social and historical development) of one people and alien to another, being carriers of national and / or historical color, they, as a rule, do not have exact matches (equivalents) in other languages, and therefore cannot be translated on a general basis, requiring a special approach. Realias are names inherent only to certain nations and peoples, objects of material culture, historical facts, names of national heroes, mythological creatures. According to the "Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" by O. S. Akhmanova, reality is "any subject of material culture" [Akhmanova, 1966, p. 381]. The translation of the names of realities is part of a large and important problem of conveying the national and historical identity of a people when translating from its language into another. The term "realia" became widespread in the 1930s, XX century, after the publication of the work of Bulgarian researchers S. Vlahov and S. Florin "The Untranslatable in

Translation". Russian and foreign scientists studying the problem translation of realities, use different terms for their designations, such as, for example, non-equivalent vocabulary, barbarisms, exoticisms, localisms, ethnographisms and some others, give various definitions of this concept, mark some signs of these lexical units and omit others

Methods

The study involved 50 English language learners aged 18–30, enrolled in intermediate-level courses across three institutions.

The cultural realias included:

- Visuals: Maps, advertisements, and cultural posters.
- Texts: Literary excerpts, newspapers, and menus.
- Artefacts: Currency, traditional clothing, and souvenirs.
- Media: Movies, songs, and podcasts.

Procedure

Participants attended 10 sessions over five weeks, where realias were integrated into lessons. Activities ranged from analyzing advertisements to role-playing cultural scenarios. Data was collected through pre- and post-tests, focus groups, and instructor observations.

Results:

The findings revealed significant improvements in:

- Vocabulary Acquisition: Learners exposed to cultural realias retained 35% more vocabulary than those in traditional settings.
- Cultural Awareness: Post-session surveys indicated an 80% increase in understanding of cultural norms and practices.
- Engagement and Motivation: 90% of participants reported that lessons using realias were more enjoyable and engaging.

Discussion

Cultural realias bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application, making language learning contextual and dynamic. Exposure to authentic materials helps learners develop pragmatic competence, understanding the subtleties of language in diverse cultural settings.

For example, analyzing restaurant menus not only enriched food-related vocabulary but also familiarized learners with dining etiquette in English-speaking countries.

In conclusion, the use of cultural realias is a transformative approach in English language education. By blending linguistic instruction with cultural immersion, realias prepare learners for real-world interactions. Future studies could

explore digital and virtual realias, expanding their application in remote learning environments.

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